

TEACHERS' LIVED EXPERIENCES IN TEACHING SPORTS TO ELEMENTARY ATHLETES

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the elementary teachers lived experiences in teaching sports to elementary athletes at Santa Rita District, Division of Pampanga during the School Year 2025-2026. It is based on Katz (1955) Skills Theory, Sport Education Theory/Model in Physical Education of Daryl Siedentop's, and Dees as cited by Silvestre and Itaas (2020) Effect of Teachers Skills and Abilities Model on the teaching transactions of teachers. This investigation used qualitative phenomenological research design. The researcher conducted an informal interview (using interview guides) and observation on the teacher participants. All MAPEH Teachers served as the participants of the study. A thematic analysis was used in this study to methodically find, examine, and report on patterns or themes in the data gathered. The researcher come up with the following conclusions: Among all the major themes under the Lived Experiences on Teaching Physical Education, Vocation stands out as the primary theme. Among all the major themes on the Lived Experiences on the challenges on Teaching Physical Education, Lack of Facilities is considered as the main theme. Among all the major themes on the Lived Experiences on the strategies on Teaching Physical Education, the primary theme is there are Similarities on the strategies used by Physical Education teachers.

Keywords: *Teacher's Lived Experiences, Teaching Sports, Physical Education, Strategies, Challenges*

INTRODUCTION

MAPEH as a learning area is a major part of the school curriculum because if learners stay emotionally and physically healthy, they can easily focus on their studies. Students must participate in school sports to increase confidence, mental alertness, and self-esteem. Daily sports activities help students to maintain a good fitness level (Indresh, 2023). All MAPEH components effectively teach teaming, collaboration and inter-personal skills. Music is made richer by the collaboration of various instrumentalists and singers. Art forms gain a wider chance of interpretation with the fusion of various creative minds. Team sports can only succeed with effective group dynamics. Health concerns may be approached by communal actions benefiting more citizens. This inculcates the notion of being “global,” that no person can live by himself especially in this age of globalism. For the arts, positive interpersonal skills develop sensitivity, which brings depth in the creative output. Students will realize the importance of its components even with the limited time given to the course. Creative approach leads to mind stimulation, increasing interest in the course components, which will make the learning experience more significant for students (Diwa Learning Systems Inc. 2016).

Meanwhile, sports in education are an integral part of the curriculum. It helps to shape a person’s personality and contributes to their holistic development. In some ways, this subject is a demonstration of all the disciplines that one has learned in school. Every sport has its foundations in math and physics. Although many subjects are taught in the classroom, sports and physical education offer students an opportunity to be outside and exercise, as well as learning a wide range of skills. There are many educational benefits to sports, and not just for the physical. Indeed, athletics positively impacts student academic success as well as their health and lifestyle. Sports do not only improve health but also are confidence boosters. Sport isn’t all about winning. Rather, it is about achieving goals and working as a team. Friendly competition is what most sports are aiming for. MAPEH teachers have to harness the natural competitiveness and joy of sport to help students enjoy and learn to play peacefully and gain confidence. The third benefit of teaching sports is teamwork. Effective teams are made up of people who can work well together. Physical education is often the first exposure to teamwork for children (Muktadir, 2022).

Reyes, Daran and Daran (2023) study found that physical (including sports education) education teachers encountered difficulties in distance learning, such as technological issues, lack of equipment, and challenges in assessing students' performance. However, they have adopted new strategies and utilized various online tools to overcome these challenges, such as Google Meet and interactive whiteboards. Teachers also employ different strategies such as localization, differentiated learning, and prioritizing student engagement to enhance the learning process. Teachers seek technical support, engage in self-care, and reflect on their experiences to manage the challenges of distance teaching.

Silvestre and Itaas (2024) revealed that teachers' knowledge, skills and competencies in MAPEH could not be strengthened effectively and efficiently through seminars and workshops only. HEIs could offer courses that would address the needs of the MAPEH teachers contextualizing the lessons and emphasizing the 21st Century Skills particularly the critical thinking skills integrating technology. With the Special Program in the Arts tract in the K to 12 Curriculum and the program offering of CHED in the Bachelor of Culture and Arts Education, the Graduate Education could help equip these teachers by offering advance degree programs align with the need of teachers specially in terms of teaching strategies, instructional materials, mastery of content knowledge and assessment in various specializations in MAPEH. An example of a public school in the country summarizes a number of the least learned competencies (LLCs) which include assessing physical activity and habits, engaging in daily physical activity, and applying injury prevention techniques. The reason for the least learned competencies is the lack of physical exercise due to exposure to gadgets. Teachers are required to submit a Quarterly Report of Least Learned Skill/Competencies (based on MELCS) in their respective subject areas. The study was conceptualized by the researcher to describe the teachers' lived experiences in teaching sports education.

Research Questions

This study aimed to describe the elementary teacher's lived experiences in teaching sports education to Elementary Athletes at Santa Rita District, Division of Pampanga during the school year 2025-2026.

Specifically, it answered the following research questions.

1. How do the elementary MAPEH teachers described their lived experiences in teaching sports education?
2. How do the elementary teachers described their challenges in teaching sports education?
3. How do the elementary teachers described their strategies in teaching sports education?
4. What framework for teachers can be proposed to enhance the teaching of Sports?

METHODOLOGY

This study used qualitative phenomenological research design. A phenomenological study delineated the meaning of lived experiences for several individuals. The objective was to focus on what participants had in common, their shared, lived experiences (Creswell, as quoted by Realino, 2017). This study utilized the same since the researcher is personally teaching physical education having a personal knowledge, experience and interest in the real-life experiences of elementary MAPEH teachers in teaching physical education. Through

phenomenology, the researcher was able to use qualitative methods for the purpose of examining the lived experiences of the given participants. In a broad sense, the purpose and function of phenomenology is to describe particular phenomena, or the appearance of things, as lived experience (Speziale & Carpenter, 2007). Lived experiences involve the immediate consciousness of life's events prior to reflection and without interpretation and are influenced by those things that are internal or external to them. It is the lived experience that gives meaning to each individual's perception of a particular phenomenon and thus presents to the individual what is true or real in his or her life (Penner and McClement, 2008). The researcher conducted unstructured in-depth phenomenological interviews, focus-group discussions and documentary analysis as sources of data. The locale of this study is the selected three (3) public schools at Santa Rita District, Division of Pampanga namely: Santa Rita Elementary School, Becuran Elementary School, and San Juan Elementary School. Thus, each school have three (3) participants to be selected by the researcher through the purposive sampling technique times three (3) schools for a total of nine (9) participants.

Data saturation was done by having a criteria for the selection of participants as follows: they must be teachers with training in sports; they must be presently teaching physical education and they must have experience of becoming a sports coach at least in school level, district, division, region and up to the national levels. Through sharing their individual experiences, the researcher was able to gain an overall lived perceptions and experiences on the areas influencing the following: the elementary teachers lived experiences in teaching physical education; their challenges in teaching physical education; and their strategies in teaching physical education. A thematic analysis was used in this study to methodically find, examine, and report on patterns or themes in the data gathered. According to Braun and Clarke as cited by Hermosilla et al (2024), thematic analysis is an all-encompassing and adaptable method that enables researchers to delve into the complex, context-bound meanings contained in the data (Hermosilla et al, 2024).

RESULTS

1. **MAPEH teachers lived experiences in teaching sports education.** The following described the Elementary MAPEH teachers lived experiences in teaching sports education.

Table 1	
Themes and Core Ideas on Lived Experiences on Teaching Sports Education	
Major Themes	Core Ideas
Calling/Vocation	<i>fun (and interesting) to teach physical education</i>

	<i>when your athletes win awards, these are the most rewarding moments</i>
	<i>time and duty is critical to physical education teachers</i>
	<i>teaching MAPEH makes me happy</i>
	<i>MAPEH is enjoyable to teach</i>
	<i>most rewarding aspect is the fulfillment</i>
	<i>full dedication is a must</i>
Skilled and Well-trained teachers	<i>teachers must be well trained because elementary athletes are still playful</i>
	<i>patience is the key</i>
	<i>continuous sports training is a must, but do not be overconfident</i>
	<i>peer collaboration (with fellow sports teachers, coaches, etc.) is a must</i>
	<i>administrators or higher ups expects winnings</i>
Demanding curriculum	<i>struggling in terms of time for both training to my athletes and teaching</i>
	<i>accepting the challenges (positive attitude) of teaching</i>
	<i>sports coaching eats time, yet it is okay for teachers</i>
	<i>have some access to curriculum resources</i>
	<i>administrators or higher ups expects winnings</i>

After their in-depth interviews, the participants shared similar perspectives, opinions, experiences regarding the elementary MAPEH teachers lived experiences in teaching sports education. In relation to this, the following questions were made and raised to the respected participants: How would you describe your overall experience in teaching sports to elementary athletes? What are the most rewarding aspects of teaching sports? Can you share any memorable experiences or moments while teaching sports to elementary athletes?

Under Table 1 Themes and Core Ideas on the Lived Experiences on Teaching Sports Education (followed by the following pertinent three core ideas), namely: a) Vocation; b) Skilled and Well-trained Teachers; and c) Demanding Curriculum.

Calling/Vocation

The following are the core ideas derived from the responses (data gathered) presented and then discussed to answer the first specific research problem.

*fun (and interesting) to teach physical education
when your athletes win awards, these are the most rewarding moments
time and duty is critical to physical education teachers
teaching MAPEH makes me happy
MAPEH is enjoyable to teach*

*most rewarding aspect is the fulfillment
full dedication is a must*

The statement ‘*full dedication is a must*’ as intertwined to effective teaching, the more dedicated the teachers, the more effective the same is expected. It is implied by the researcher based on Katz (1955) Skills Theory, Sport Education Theory/Model in Physical Education of Daryl Siedentop’s, and Dees as cited by Silvestre and Itaas (2020) Effect of Teachers Skills and Abilities Model.

Time and duty is indeed critical to physical education teachers. To improve the teaching of sports, physical education teachers are therefore must have time and are required to think and explore the diversified functions of teaching aids closely around improving students' Sports Core literacy. This is to integrate new educational concepts and promote the continuous update and development of subject education (Rad et al. 2024)

Skilled and Well-trained Teachers

For the second theme Skilled and Well-trained Teachers, the following are the Core Ideas of the participants:

*teachers must be well trained because elementary athletes are still playful
patience is the key
continuous sports training is a must, but do not be overconfident
peer collaboration (with fellow sports teachers, coaches, etc.) is a must
administrators or higher ups expects winnings*

The responses which state that “*peer collaboration (with fellow sports teachers, coaches, etc.) is a must*” coincides with the benefit of teaching sports teamwork stated by Muktadir (2022). Effective teams are made up of people who can work well together. Physical education is considered as the first exposure to teamwork for children (Muktadir, 2022).

Demanding Curriculum

For the third theme Demanding Curriculum, the following Core Ideas are noteworthy to state one by one:

*struggling in terms of time for both training to my athletes and teaching
accepting the challenges (positive attitude) of teaching*

*sports coaching eats time, yet it is okay for teachers
have some access to curriculum resources
administrators or higher ups expects winnings*

2. Elementary teachers challenges in teaching sports education

The following described the challenges of Elementary MAPEH teachers' lived experiences in teaching sports education.

Under Table 2 Themes and Core Ideas on Lived Experiences on the challenges on Teaching Sports Education (which were followed by the pertinent three core ideas), namely: a) Lack of Parental Support & Involvement; b) Lack of Facilities; and c) Inconsistent Sports Performance.

Table 2

Themes and Core Ideas on Lived Experiences on Challenges in Teaching Sports Education	
Major Themes	Core Ideas
Lack of Parental Support & Involvement	<i>some parents does not have money to support the training or sports of their child</i>
	<i>some parents won't allow their child to attend the training</i>
	<i>parents are very busy in their work, business, etc.</i>
	<i>parents lack of time</i>
	<i>parents are not sure on how to assist their child who are athletes</i>
Lack of Facilities	<i>lacking of infrastructure (facilities) intended for physical education</i>
	<i>lack of sports equipment</i>
	<i>no covered court</i>
	<i>learner athletes sometimes need to go out from the school just to practice their sports because the school does not have the facility</i>
	<i>inadequate school funding to improve facilities intended for sports development</i>
Inconsistent Sports Performance	<i>there are school years we are winning from competitions there are times we lost</i>

	<i>need for full support to sports and physical education from all stakeholders (administrators, parents, community support, etc.)</i>
	<i>due to lack of sports equipment, facilities, etc.</i>

After the participants in-depth interviews, the same shared personal perspectives, opinions, experiences regarding the challenges of elementary MAPEH teachers lived experiences in teaching sports education. Related to this, the following questions were asked to the respected participants: What challenges do you face when teaching sports in elementary schools? How do factors such as class size, facilities, and available equipment affect your ability to teach sports effectively? What are the common difficulties learners face in participating in sports activities, and how do you address them? How does the level of interest and participation of learners impact your teaching strategies?

Table 2 Themes and Core Ideas on the challenges (Lived Experiences) on Teaching Sports Education are the three core ideas, namely: a) Lack of Parental Support & Involvement; b) Lack of Facilities; and c) Inconsistent Sports Performance.

Lack of Parental Support and Involvement

Of the many core ideas conceptualized in this chapter, Lack of Parental Support and Involvement stands out as being primary among teachers. The following are the core ideas founded from the responses then were discussed to answer the second research problem.

some parents does not have money to support the training or sports of their child
some parents won't allow their child to attend the training
parents are very busy in their work, business, etc.
parents lack of time
parents are not sure on how to assist their child who are athletes

Lack of Facilities

When considering the second theme which is the Lack of Facilities it is necessary to mention the following core ideas:

lacking of infrastructure (facilities) intended for physical education
lack of sports equipment
no covered court
learner athletes sometimes need to go out from the school just to practice their sports because the school does not have the facility
inadequate school funding to improve facilities intended for sports development

These statements cemented the idea on the facilities intended for sports development. Karemu et al (2024) found out that schools with better-developed sports facilities are favorably positioned to report better student participation and their performance in sports.

Inconsistent Sports Performance

Of the themes mentioned in this chapter, Inconsistent Sports Performance is necessary to put into full details. The following are the core ideas taken from the responses that was discussed to answer the second research problem.

there are school years we are winning from competitions there are times we lost need for full support to sports and physical education from all stakeholders (administrators, parents, community support, etc.).

Karemu et al (2024) stress that the allocation of sports facilities resources in public schools must be an agenda of school administrators, policy planners, etc.
due to lack of sports equipment, facilities, etc.

Likewise, Peter .and Fatai (2021) observed that in many public schools, the students have limited options of sporting events they can participate in due to lack or inadequacy of sports facilities.

3. Elementary teachers’ strategies in teaching sports education

The following described the strategies of Elementary MAPEH teachers lived experiences in teaching sports education.

Table 3 shows the Themes and Core Ideas on Lived Experiences on the Strategies in Teaching Sports Education are the pertinent three core ideas, namely: a) Similarities; b) Dissimilarities.

Table 3	
Themes and Core Ideas on Lived Experiences on Strategies in Teaching Sports Education	
Major Themes	Core Ideas
Similarities	<i>Constructivism</i>
	<i>any teaching strategies that promote discipline, teamwork and sportsmanship</i>
	<i>strategies that focus on constant practice</i>
	<i>Differentiated Instruction is always used to teach athletes</i>
Dissimilarities	<i>Personalized Coaching/Teaching</i>
	<i>some teachers give more lectures other don't</i>
	<i>some teachers or coaches provide consistent support throughout their learner athletes career, some are not</i>

	<i>most teachers desire for professional development in relation to teaching strategies and practices, a few of the same do not desire</i>
	<i>most teachers give all their time during learners' athletes practices, a few of the same just give instructions</i>
	<i>some teachers adjust their teaching approaches to better learners' circumstances as athletes, some do not adjust</i>

Similarities

Of the themes mentioned in this chapter, the strategies employed by the Elementary MAPEH teachers lived experiences in teaching sports education have Similarities and Dissimilarities. The following are the core ideas expressed into writing to answer the third research problem.

Constructivism
any teaching strategies that promote discipline, teamwork and sportsmanship
strategies that focus on constant practice
Differentiated Instruction is always used to teach athletes
Personalized Coaching/Teaching

Indeed, '*Personalized Coaching/Teaching*' students helps the same to increase learners' confidence, mental alertness, and self-esteem in terms of sports (Indresh, 2023).

Dissimilarities

The following are the core ideas named as Dissimilarities as supplemental core ideas to also answer the third and second to the last research problem.

some teachers give more lectures other don't
some teachers or coaches provide consistent support throughout their learner
athletes career, some are not
most teachers desire for professional development in relation to teaching
strategies and practices, a few of the same do not desire
most teachers give all their time during learners' athletes practices, a few of the
same just give instructions
some teachers adjust their teaching approaches to better learners' circumstances
as athletes, some do not adjust

Sports teachers must avoid lectures instead of using engaging teaching strategies. Wallace (2022) found that quality student-faculty relationships impacted their perceptions of self-directedness, motivation, engagement, student satisfaction, and academic achievement.

DISCUSSION

The following are the three (3) major themes under the Lived Experiences on Teaching Physical Education, namely: a) Vocation; b) Skilled and Well-trained Teachers; and c) Demanding Curriculum. The following are the three (3) major themes on the Lived Experiences on the challenges on Teaching Physical Education (which were followed by the pertinent three core ideas), namely: a) Lack of Parental Support & Involvement; b) Lack of Facilities; and c) Inconsistent Sports Performance. The following are the three (3) major themes on the Lived Experiences on the strategies on Teaching Physical Education (which were followed by the pertinent three core ideas), namely: a) Similarities and b) Dissimilarities. The Proposed framework for teachers to enhance the teaching of Sports is entitled “Improving, Continuing, Quality Sports Access, Training, Development and Teaching (ICQS) framework”.

Conclusions

The researcher, with reference to the summary of findings, has enumerated the following conclusions:

1. Among all the major themes under the Lived Experiences on Teaching sports education, Vocation stands out as the primary theme.
2. Among all the major themes on the Lived Experiences on the challenges on Teaching sports education, Lack of Facilities is considered as the main theme.
3. Among all the major themes on the Lived Experiences on the strategies on Teaching sports education, the primary theme is there are Similarities on the strategies used by sports education teachers.

Recommendations

This researcher come up with the following recommendations:

1. The school administrator may propose a curricular program such as special program in sports that focuses on the delivery of a high-quality, well designed physical education and sports curriculum.
2. The school sports education teachers may not use lectures often instead employ actual drills, practices, training, etc.
3. The school sports education teachers may aim to involve themselves on the annual professional development opportunities to enhance their instructional skills and techniques.
4. The school sports education teachers may desire for professional development in relation to teaching strategies and practices.
5. The school sports education teachers may give all their time during learners' athletes practices.
6. The school stakeholders may address the lack of appropriate equipment and facilities used for physical education and sports.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Participants in this study (elementary MAPEH teachers) were fully informed about the nature of the investigation, its goals, and consequences. The emphasis was on voluntary involvement, freedom to participate or withdraw anytime, in keeping with respect for individuals. The participants' well-being benefits were prioritized, which is the duty to optimize benefits and reduce harm. Fair participant selection and equitable burden and benefit sharing in research are mandated by the principle of justice. The study was inclusive, ensuring that many perspectives are heard (Hermosilla et al, 2024) or the elementary MAPEH teachers in the whole division. Finally, the researcher used the findings ethically through the following: Share results in an accessible language with participants, stakeholders, and the public; Collaborate with communities, when possible, to determine the best way to present findings; Avoid overgeneralizations; contextualize results within the specific samples studied.

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